

**CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING CADETS' COMPETENCE
IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES****Jarilkasinova Gulnaz Khojabayevna****Senior Lecturer, Department of Foreign Languages 1,
Tashkent University of Applied Sciences****Email: gulnozajarilkasinova@gmail.com****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20900094>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 21st June 2026Accepted: 23rd June 2026Online: 25th June 2026**KEYWORDS**

*technologies, competence,
methods, didactic tool,
motivation, processor, graphics,
computer*

ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the criteria for evaluating the professional competence of cadets in information and also communication technologies in English language.

Introduction

In recent years, special attention has been paid in the Republic of Uzbekistan to teaching foreign languages through information and communication technologies, and a number of reforms have been implemented in this area. Important objectives have been established, including ensuring “a high level and quality of training personnel who possess modern information and communication technologies and have a profound command of foreign languages.” Based on international experience, the organizational framework for foreign language teaching has been improved, and the regulatory and material-technical foundations for developing learners’ linguistic and sociolinguistic competencies have been created. Significant tasks have also been identified, such as clarifying the methodology, system, and linguodidactic foundations for developing the professional competencies of military educators in teaching English, as well as conducting scientific research aimed at strengthening productive and receptive skills.

The study takes into account the provisions related to educational quality assurance outlined in several legal and regulatory documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including Presidential Decree No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017, “On the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”; Presidential Decree No. PF-5789 of August 27, 2019, “On the Introduction of a System of Continuous Professional Development for Leaders and Teaching Staff of Higher Educational Institutions”; Resolution No. PQ-1875 of December 10, 2012, “On Measures for Further Improving the System of Foreign Language Learning”; Resolution No. PQ-2909 of April 20, 2017, “On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System”; and Resolution No. PQ-4375 of June 28, 2019, “On Additional Measures to Improve the System of Educating Youth in the Spirit of Military Patriotism and Preparing a Reserve of Personnel for the Armed Forces and Public Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan,” as well as other relevant legal documents.

Assessment criteria for developing cadets' competence in information-methodological support were developed. These criteria include the level of cadets' knowledge, skills, and abilities in information-methodological support, as well as their motivation.

Literature review and methods

According to S. Konyushenko [52], the competence of future cadets in the field of information and communication technologies is understood as an integrative characteristic formed on the basis of specialized knowledge, skills, and abilities related to a particular academic discipline. It reflects a student's readiness and ability to make effective decisions and apply efficient methods in professional activities using modern information and communication technologies.

The effectiveness of using information and communication technologies in teaching academic subjects can be ensured only when teachers demonstrate sufficient interest in their application, possess a broad outlook, master both general and specialized educational software, and clearly understand the role of ICT within the methodological system of teaching the subject [103; 104].

M. Lebedeva and O. Shilova [56] distinguished three stages in the development of ICT competence: basic, general, and professional. They also emphasized the distinction between the use of ICT in educational activities and its application in solving professional tasks.

Based on the first criterion, four levels of development of cadets' competence in information-methodological support can be identified.

Levels of Cadets' Competence in Information-Methodological Support

Level	Description
High	Demonstrates a clear understanding of the laws and principles governing information-methodological support. Selects methods based on its principles and tools to solve assigned tasks and explains them from the perspective of future professional activity.
Medium	Does not always demonstrate an understanding of the laws and principles governing information-methodological support. Selects appropriate methods but experiences difficulties in justifying them and cannot fully explain their relevance to future professional activities.
Low	Makes errors in understanding the laws and principles of information-methodological support and fails to analyze them. Relies primarily on existing knowledge when selecting methods and tools to solve assigned tasks.

Is unable to demonstrate an understanding of the laws and principles governing information-methodological support and experiences difficulties in selecting appropriate methods and tools for solving tasks.

The criteria for assessing cadets' motivation toward information-methodological support include:

The level of initiative and activity demonstrated in learning and cognitive activities.

The degree of responsibility shown for the outcomes of assigned tasks and activities

In the process of teaching the subject “Foreign Language,” the effective application of methods for monitoring cadets’ knowledge and skills requires the creation of a system of educational tasks. Educational tasks designed to assess knowledge and skills serve as a leading didactic tool aimed at developing cadets’ independence, initiative, activity, and thinking abilities. Continuous completion of such tasks promotes the development of independent thinking, while the intellectual activities formed during the learning process contribute to the continuous development of cognitive abilities.

To achieve this objective, it is important not only to employ diverse teaching methods during lessons but also to assign tasks of varying content and complexity. Assessment tasks designed for different levels of mastery allow cadets to acquire educational material according to their individual capabilities and learning potential.

Conclusion

The examples discussed above demonstrate that the stages for developing cadets’ competence in information-methodological support within the teaching of the course “Informatics and Information Technologies” have been identified in all military higher educational institutions.

Stage 1: Development and systematization of cadets’ knowledge in information-methodological support.

Stage 2: Development of practical skills and abilities for working with information-methodological support software.

Stage 3: Development of skills and competencies enabling cadets to apply information-methodological support in their future professional activities.

Furthermore:

4.A methodology for teaching information-methodological support was developed on the basis of modern pedagogical and information technologies.

5.Methodological materials were created for conducting four hours of theoretical instruction on information-methodological support within the teaching of the “Foreign Language” course.

6.Two practical sessions and four laboratory activities were designed to develop cadets’ skills and competencies in working with information-methodological support.

Assessment criteria were developed for evaluating cadets’ competence in information-methodological support in the process of teaching the subject “Foreign Language” at military higher educational institutions.

References:

- 1.President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2017, February 7). Decree No. PF-4947 “On the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.” Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
- 2.President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2018, September 21). Decree No. PF-5544 “On Approval of the Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019–2021.” Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
- 3.President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2019, August 27). Decree No. PF-5789 “On the Introduction of a System of Continuous Professional Development for Leaders and Teaching Staff of Higher Educational Institutions.” Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

- 4.Andreev, A. A. (1998–1999). Didactic possibilities of information telecommunications tools and technologies in the system of distance education. Retrieved from <http://www.ito.su/h/andreev-t.html>
- 5.Aripov, M., & Muhammadiev, A. (2004). Informatics and information technologies: A textbook for higher educational institutions. Tashkent: TDYUI. 275 p.
- 6.Asekretov, O. K., Borisov, B. A., Bugakova, N. Yu., et al. (2015). Modern educational technologies: Pedagogy and psychology (Monograph). Novosibirsk: SRNS Publishing House. 318 p. Retrieved from <http://science.vvsu.ru/files/5040BK65-273B-44BB-98K4-KB5092BE4460.pdf>
- 7.Bagaeva, I. D. (2000). Professionalism of pedagogical activity: Essence and structure. In Professionalism of the Teacher: Abstracts of Reports and Communications. Izhevsk–St. Petersburg.
- 8.Bakieva, G. Kh. (2003). Semanteme: Content and expression. Issues of Philology, 2, 5–8. Tashkent: Uzbek State World Languages University.
- 9.Begimkulov, U. Sh. (2004). The use of modern information and communication technologies in the professional development system. Public Education, 6, 132–137. Tashkent.